

The Menu of Good Governance: an online governance decision support tool - D 4.3

WP 4 - T 4.3

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document aims to present The Menu of Good Governance (hereafter The Menu), an online decision-support tool designed to provide policymakers and practitioners with actionable solutions for Food Sharing Initiatives (FSI). The Menu empowers users to create and implement effective rules, processes, collaborations and programs for food sharing by offering proven strategies and insights derived from successful European examples. The Menu was created in the context of the EU CULTIVATE project to highlight practical solutions to the common barriers faced by food-sharing projects, helping decision-makers and practitioners plan and execute their efforts efficiently and effectively for the benefit of both local and global communities.

What is CULTIVATE?

CULTIVATE is a four-year Innovation Action funded by the EU Horizon Europe (GA No. 101083377) to increase public awareness and knowledge of FSI, to understand what drives or hampers their practice, and to help stakeholders navigate food sharing landscapes and cultures to understand, develop, replicate, scale out, and strengthen food sharing. The ultimate goal of the project is to create more sustainable, resilient, and healthy urban and peri-urban food systems. CULTIVATE will co-design a groundbreaking online social innovation support platform – The Food Sharing Compass – in collaboration with FSI, local authorities, food supply actors, researchers and citizens to: map, track and monitor UPU food sharing landscapes; identify the costs, benefits and impacts of FSI; help actors navigate governance architectures and ensure appropriate policies and regulations of food sharing; support increased citizen engagement in UPU food sharing; and create a community of practice for FSI. Working collaboratively with multiple actors, CULTIVATE will develop more sustainable, resilient, and healthy UPU food systems that support the inclusive climate mitigation and adaptation ambitions of the EU. The Menu of Good Governance has been developed as part of CULTIVATE's Work Package 4 Comparative Governance Analysis.

What is Food Sharing?

Food sharing involves collective actions related to food and its associated items, spaces, skills, and knowledge (Davies & Evans, 2019). While food sharing can take place between friends, families, neighbours, communities, and strangers across the food system - including activities like growing, cooking, and eating together, or surplus food redistribution-, in CULTIVATE we focus on food sharing beyond friends and family, and specifically initiatives explicitly set up to share food. We refer to these as Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs). FSIs adopt different organisational forms, including co-operatives and social enterprises, charities, and for-profits, and can be community, private-sector or state-led (Davies, 2020). Examples include seed libraries, community gardens, food-related co-operatives, community kitchens, and surplus food redistribution organisations.

In what follows, we explain the Menu of Good Governance prototype, highlighting, on the one hand, what we understand by good governance, and on the other, describing the key functionalities and navigation instructions of The Menu. Secondly, we elaborate on the methodology used to collect data and develop The Menu. We then describe the strategy for replicating The Menu and conclude with some final remarks.

2. THE MENU OF GOOD GOVERNANCE

The Menu provides inspiring practices to strengthen food sharing governance across Europe and beyond. The resource is a curated repository of diverse approaches that work towards social and environmental solutions in various European contexts. These approaches may help institutions, the private sector, civil society and communities navigate the complexities of FSI governance, addressing challenges such as regulatory barriers, limited resources, or a lack of stakeholder coordination.

The Menu is divided into five sections:

- *About*: This section provides an introduction to the tool, including background information on the Food Sharing Compass and the CULTIVATE project.
- *Methodology*: This section provides a brief overview of the methodological approach used in the development of The Menu, along with hyperlinks to relevant resources. Additionally, a downloadable PDF is available, offering a detailed description of the methodology.
- *Key Terms*: This section defines the terminology used throughout The Menu. Users can scroll through this section to gain a better understanding of key concepts and categories.
- *How to Use It*: This section guides users on navigating and searching within The Menu, including an instructional video that demonstrates a sample search process.
- *Get in touch*: This section features a contact form for users to submit examples of good governance practices, as well as an email address for direct communication.

The Menu can be publicly accessed here: <https://www.menuofgoodgovernance.eu/>

2.1. What is Good Governance?

Good governance is closely tied to the broader concept of governance. Although its early emphasis was on state-centred approaches to managing public issues, such perspectives are now considered outdated since they overlooked stakeholder interactions and process dynamics (Zerbian & Luis Romero, 2023). As an evolving and dynamic concept, governance can be understood and applied to politics and policymaking in various ways. In the context of the food system, governance refers to the institutions, actors, rules, norms, and power relations that shape how food is

produced, distributed, accessed, consumed, and wasted (Margulis & Duncan, 2016). Governance operates through competing and overlapping networks of interacting actors who draw on diverse resources and forms of power to influence outcomes (Canfield, 2021). In any given context, governance concerns the strategic dimensions of guiding and shaping direction—it involves not only determining where to go, but also who gets to participate in the decision-making process and in what roles.

Good governance, however, represents a more proactive and constructive approach to governance. It emphasises the importance of institutions, organisations, and other social actors engaging in democratic and equitable processes to overcome barriers and deliver public goods for both society and the environment (Graham, Plumptre & Amos, 2003). Rather than a fixed endpoint, good governance is better understood as an ongoing and dynamic process (Zerbian & Luis Romero, 2023). This perspective of governance calls for the inclusion of diverse societal actors in decision-making processes. While it can take many different forms, its foundation lies in ethical, responsible, and fair decision-making. This approach functions across multiple levels—ranging from the local to the international—and extends beyond government to involve diverse stakeholders, thereby contributing to the democratization of the food system. In fact, the interactions among governance actors shape the specific characteristics of good governance, which can generate both positive and negative outcomes (Zerbian & Luis Romero, 2023). Moreover, it is important to note that, as good governance practices can be applied across different contexts, they require adaptation. This means that good governance is not fixed but evolves in relation to place.

Several international institutions, including the European Union, the OECD, and the World Bank, have established key principles of good governance. Drawing from these and other recognised principles of good governance in the literature (FAO, 2014; OHCHR, 2025; Zerbian & Luis Romero, 2023), we identify the following as particularly relevant to the implementation of food sharing solutions.

Participation: People must have the opportunity to engage directly or indirectly in the planning, design, monitoring, and evaluation of decisions that impact their lives.

Transparency: Decision-making and implementation processes should follow clear and established rules. Key information must be readily accessible, understandable, and openly shared with those affected, ensuring clarity and trust.

Inclusiveness: Governance must be free from discrimination or exclusion of any group, whether based on gender, ethnicity, religion, or other characteristics. All groups should have meaningful representation and participation in relevant processes and initiatives.

Accountability: Government institutions and other social actors must be held accountable to those they serve. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation of

performance and processes are essential to ensure they are meeting their responsibilities.

On the Menu website, we offer a brief and accessible introduction to the concept of good governance, prioritising clarity and outreach over academic depth in order to engage a wider audience.

2.2. Functionalities and navigation

To begin exploring The Menu, visit the homepage using the provided link. From there, users can navigate to sections like About, Methodology, Key Terms, How to Use It, or Get in Touch via the buttons on the main page (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Banner of the MGG with sections

In addition to navigating each section displayed in The Menu, users can also scroll down to view all available entries or use the drop-down menus to browse by specific criteria (see Figure 2). Selecting an individual entry provides a description of a concrete example of good governance practice and explains how this practice contributes to a solution. Each entry is enriched with a detailed description of the practice, a relevant link for further information, suggestions for similar practices, tags indicating key characteristics, such as city size (if applicable), geographic region, type of solution, level of intervention, and stakeholders involved, and a link to additional resources for deeper exploration. Users can also share each practice directly via their social media platforms.

Figure 2: Examples of entries at the Menu of Good Governance

To enhance usability, The Menu offers a search function and multiple filtering options. On the main page, users can enter keywords in the search bar or apply filters by Type of food sharing, Solution, or Stakeholder (see Figure 3). Additionally, users can tailor the displayed entries using additional filters, such as city size, geographic scope, or level of intervention (see Figure 4).

Figure 3: Main search filters: Type of food sharing, Solution, or Stakeholder

Figure 4: Additional filters: city size, geographic scope, or level of intervention

In short, to navigate The Menu users can:

1. Use the main buttons on the homepage to access key sections such as About, Methodology, Key Terms, How to Use It, or Get in Touch.
2. Scroll down to browse all entries, or use the drop-down menus and side filters to refine results by specific criteria.
3. Click on an individual entry to open it. Within the entry, scroll down to view a detailed description, an external link (if available), and suggestions for similar practices.

Regarding the type of food sharing initiative, The Menu has adopted three main categories of food sharing, defined as follows, according to the *Food Sharing Dictionary* (Dean, Davies, & Nicoletta, 2023):

- *Food waste recovery and redistribution*: This category encompasses initiatives that intercept surplus food—such as unsold groceries, excess agricultural production, or leftover meals—that would otherwise be discarded. These initiatives harvest, locate, collect, sort, and redistribute this food to individuals and communities, with a focus on supporting those facing food insecurity.
- *Community gardening*: This category includes initiatives involving gardens created for communal use and enjoyment. It encompasses activities such as jointly occupying garden spaces, sharing gardening skills, offering access to garden plots, and collectively using and appreciating garden environments.
- *Community cooking and meal sharing*: This category includes initiatives centered around a shared kitchen designed for communal use and enjoyment, as well as those that involve eating together, offering meals to others, or collectively using, occupying, and appreciating meal-related knowledge, skills, tools, and spaces.

Regarding solutions, The Menu presents in-progress solutions organised into four categories, each corresponding to a key topic related to overcoming the barriers commonly encountered by food-sharing initiatives. These categories are the result of the comprehensive research process focused on the governance of food sharing initiatives described in section 3 of this document. These categories are:

- *Structural Factors and Local Conditions* focus on solutions that relate to the political, economic, social, cultural, and environmental contexts—both local and global—that influence Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs). These solutions might be suggested as lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic and economic crisis, or they might be tackling the climate emergency, structural problems contributing to food insecurity, and social inequalities. Alternatively, these solutions may be linked to recognising the local aspects that shape FSIs and their impacts.
- *Regulatory and Policy Frameworks* can shape and encourage FSI-related activities and their impacts. This category includes laws—both direct and indirect—official guidelines, incentives, and actions aimed at enhancing coherence across administrative levels, along with monitoring measures that help shape and encourage the effectiveness of FSIs.
- *Resources, Knowledge, and Discourses* are necessary to ensure the development of FSIs that deliver sustainability benefits. This category includes funding, infrastructure, food resources, spaces, paid human resources, voluntary work, public or common resources, and the necessary technological and bureaucratic skills and tools. This category also considers the role of

discourse among various stakeholders and the power dynamics involved, which can significantly support the growth and success of FSIs.

- *Participation, Internal Organisation, and Networks* highlight elements that can foster the development of both internal and external relationships among key FSI actors and various stakeholders. These solutions may involve building alliances, creating networks, and forging collaborations, as well as establishing rules to improve internal organisational processes, fostering interactions with the local communities, and enhancing overall participation in the initiative.

With the Stakeholder filter, The Menu allows users to sort practices based on the main actors involved—such as public sector bodies, private sector organisations, or food sharing initiatives themselves.

3. METHODOLOGY

The Menu is the result of a comprehensive research process focused on the governance of food sharing initiatives that took place over a period of two and a half years, from March 2023 to the publication of the pilot at the end of October 2025 (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Research process on food sharing governance culminating in the publication of the Pilot of the Menu of Good Governance

This process involved a review of the international literature on food sharing governance, along with a qualitative analysis of the governance landscapes in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht. This analysis was further enriched by inputs from multi-actor workshops held in each city, which explored future scenarios for food sharing. Additionally, the research incorporated a curated selection of best governance practices contributed by member organisations of the CULTIVATE Consortium. What follows is a detailed description of this comprehensive process.

3.1. Review of international literature on food sharing governance

We employed a scoping review methodology to map the field of food-sharing governance in European cities. Scoping reviews help clarify concepts, identify knowledge gaps, and guide future research (Munn et al., 2018).

A methodological protocol was developed in advance to guide the review, focusing key questions on how governance shapes—and is shaped by—urban food sharing initiatives. Specifically, the review explored:

- The social, environmental, and economic benefits of food sharing in European cities;
- How governance is addressed in academic literature;
- The main enablers and barriers to urban food-sharing initiatives;
- Existing knowledge gaps in the field.

A total of 58 studies were identified as eligible for inclusion in the scoping review and were analysed in relation to the guiding questions.

The findings of this review are published in an academic paper (see Herrero & Moragues-Faus, 2025). They include the aggregated environmental, social, and economic benefits associated with urban food-sharing initiatives, as identified in the literature. The findings also examine both internal and external dimensions of food sharing governance, outlining the key enablers and barriers reported across the selected studies. Additionally, we also propose a classification framework for these enablers and barriers, which lays the foundation for the solutions clusters presented in The Menu (see the section on Clustering Governance Solutions).

Additionally, the review process also culminated in the publication of a [policy brief on food sharing](#).

3.2. Analysis of the governance landscapes

As part of the research process on food sharing governance, we also carried out a landscape governance analysis in three European cities: Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht. The analysis focused on how FSI develop within different governance and socio-ecological contexts, specifically within three domains: food waste recovery and redistribution, community gardens, and the food-related social and solidarity economy. In each city, the study examined the cultural, environmental, regulatory, and policy conditions that influence these initiatives, aiming to identify key enablers and barriers to their sustainability, as well as formulate policy recommendations tailored to different sectors, stakeholders, and city contexts.

To ensure comparability across cities, a shared research protocol was developed and followed by each city team. This protocol guided both the desk-based research and the qualitative data collection. The research was structured around three guiding questions:

- How are regulatory regimes shaping food sharing landscapes, and what is their impact on FSIs?
- What are the main place-based enablers and barriers to sustainable food sharing in the three cities?
- What is the influence of cultural and socio-ecological contexts in shaping FSIs?

The desk-based research involved online searches through local, regional, and national administrative repositories, supported by knowledge provided by city administration partners. Searches were carried out using a set of predefined keywords (translated into local languages) and adapted by each local team to reflect the specific context. Documents were selected if they related to relevant governance categories, such as local strategic plans and programmes, legislation, regulations, projects, official reports, or existing studies on food sharing governance. Each city also included other types of documentation considered relevant to its local setting.

To complement the desk research, a total of 42 semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders were conducted (15 interviews in Barcelona, 15 in Utrecht and 12 in Milan). These included food sharing practitioners, public officials, and other relevant actors. Participants were selected to ensure diverse representation across the three food sharing domains, a range of administrative levels and positions, and attention to gender and minority inclusion. Interviewees were required to have in-depth experience in at least one of the food sharing domains and to be well-acquainted with the local context.

The combined analysis of documents and interviews in each city enabled the identification of common and context-specific enablers and barriers to effective food sharing governance. These findings not only informed the policy recommendations developed for each city but also served as the foundation for structuring the types of solutions presented in the Menu of Good Governance. The methodology also benefited from insights gathered during multi-actor workshops held in the three cities, which helped explore future scenarios and validate the research findings (see section 3.3).

The governance landscape reports for [Barcelona](#), [Milan](#), and [Utrecht](#) are available in an online repository, along with a [comparative analysis](#) that highlights similarities and differences across the three cities.

3.3. Futuring scenario workshops

Futures thinking—or *futuring*—provides powerful tools for understanding the complexity of food systems and envisioning transformative pathways (Fitzgerald &

Davies, 2022; Hebinck et al., 2022; Muiderman et al., 2020; Fergnani, 2019). Among these tools, scenario planning stands out for its capacity to bring together diverse stakeholders to collaboratively explore possible futures, surface tensions, and co-design more inclusive and sustainable trajectories. By integrating multiple perspectives, scenario planning promotes collaborative decision-making, challenges dominant assumptions, and supports the development of forward-looking, resilient strategies (Hebinck et al. 2022).

This methodology was applied and refined through a series of participatory scenario planning workshops held in Barcelona, Milan, and Utrecht. These workshops were designed as spaces to imagine possible futures for food sharing, develop strategies to address emerging uncertainties, and improve the long-term resilience and planning capacity of local initiatives and institutions.

The workshops followed a participatory and inclusive approach, using future scenarios and backcasting to identify key barriers and enablers, as well as to co-develop a set of actionable strategies. Participants engaged in collective visioning exercises, examined how different actors might respond to evolving contexts, and mapped out transition pathways towards more just and sustainable urban food systems.

These workshops made a direct contribution to the *Menu of Good Governance* by:

- Revealing governance barriers faced by food sharing initiatives across different urban contexts
- Identifying practical solutions and conditions that enable or constrain their implementation
- Informing the clustering of good governance practices presented in The Menu
- Strengthening the capacity of local stakeholders to act collectively and strategically in the face of uncertainty

In this way, the scenario planning workshops served not only as a methodological innovation but also as a catalyst for generating the insights, solutions, and collaborations that underpin the *Menu of Good Governance*.

The guidebook on inclusive, participatory and resilient sustainable urban food sharing scenario planning can be found [here](#).

3.4. Collaborative curation of best governance practices

The University of Barcelona coordinated the development of The Menu with the support of CULTIVATE partners and several external collaborators. The curation of best governance practices spanned approximately eight months and involved a collaborative effort among several Consortium partners. University of Barcelona,

PEMB, Milan City Council, Wageningen University, Lund University, Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, and ICLEI played an active role in identifying and contributing good governance practices to the database.

Additionally, dedicated exercises were designed and carried out during two General Assemblies to collect good governance practices from Consortium participants. In each session, participants were divided into groups of eight to encourage dialogue and exchange of knowledge about relevant practices from their local contexts and beyond (see Figure 6). We also conducted structured interviews with several FSI within the Consortium to gather their insights and experiences related to good governance practices.

Figure 6: Cultivate Consortium exercise on The Menu during General Assembly in Barcelona 2025

In total, we collaboratively gathered 217 good governance practices.

Figure 7 presents the distribution of good governance practices across different food sharing areas. The largest share of identified governance practices is associated with Community Gardens (39.3%). Food Waste Recovery projects account for a substantial 33.8% of the practices. In contrast, Community Cooking initiatives represent a smaller proportion (14.9%). The category All three—encompassing projects that integrate gardens, cooking, and waste recovery—accounts for 11.9%.

Count of FOOD SHARING AREA

Figure 7. Percentage of good governance practices by food sharing area

Figure 8 shifts the lens to the types of solutions in which governance practices are embedded. Here, Participation and Internal Processes emerge as the dominant category (33.8%). Resources, Knowledge and Discourse follows closely at 30.1%. Structural Factors and Conditions account for 20.8%. Finally, Regulatory and Policy measures comprise 15.3% of the identified practices.

Count of WHAT CATEGORY OF ENABLERS THE PRACTICE BELONGS TO?

Figure 8. Percentage of good governance practices by solution category

Figure 9 illustrates the distribution of good governance practices according to city size. The majority of identified practices occur in large cities, which account for 56.2% of the total. A notable proportion of cases—29.5%—are classified as Not applicable, suggesting that many practices operate at a regional, national, or international scale. Small cities represent 7.8% of the cases, while medium-sized cities account for 6.5%.

Figure 9. Percentage of good governance practices by city size

4. REPLICATION

Between June 2025 and October 2026 (Months 30 to 45 of the project), the replication phase of The Menu of Good Governance will take place in two Spoke locations: Dublin and Brighton & Hove. Led by Dublin City Council and the Brighton & Hove Food Partnership, this phase is designed to test and validate the tool developed through the co-design process in Work Package 4. The goal is to evaluate how The Menu can support the creation of enabling governance environments for sustainable urban food sharing across diverse local contexts. By implementing the tool in these two distinct cities, the project will assess its adaptability, usability, and impact, generating insights into its broader applicability and potential for scaling.

With guidance from the University of Barcelona (UB), each Spoke partner will identify key governance challenges, define leverage points, and select appropriate strategies

to address them, such as adjusting market or financial incentives, offering training, or fostering alliances. The replication process will follow a structured approach.

First, key actors from a selected food sharing sector—including public authorities, food sharing initiatives, and private stakeholders—will be identified and invited to participate. Each participant will then engage in individual experimentation with the online Menu pilot. This phase will help assess the tool’s usability, identify barriers, and evaluate the relevance of the practices provided. Support materials, such as an instructional video and an evaluation template, will be provided.

Following individual testing, a participatory workshop will be held. In this workshop, participants will discuss the governance challenges encountered, define collective barriers, identify leverage points, and explore solutions drawn from the MGG. Activities will include evaluating the applicability of selected practices, identifying gaps, and mapping influence pathways to understand who needs to be engaged to implement change effectively.

Insights and feedback from this process will inform the final refinement of the Menu, enhancing its practical value and usability. The improved version of the tool will then be integrated into the broader *Food Sharing Compass*, supporting cities in advancing sustainable and inclusive food governance.

5. CONCLUSION

This deliverable summarises the process and output of WP4, the Menu of Good Governance - an online governance decision support tool. The Menu will be featured on the CULTIVATE website and embedded in the Food Sharing Compass. In 2025-2026, The Menu will be replicated and adapted in CULTIVATE’s two Spokes locations: Dublin and Brighton & Hove. Based on the replication outcome, The Menu will be updated and enhanced accordingly. The Menu will remain active until at least 2035 and will be updated annually. We welcome new good governance practices to add to the menu by submitting a form.

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